

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[Complex branching]** smell? *

When a function assumes the responsibility of handling multiple errors alone, it can increase its cyclomatic complexity (metric of control-flow) and become incomprehensible. This situation can configure a specific instance of "Long function", a traditional code smell, but has implications of its own. Under these circumstances, this function could get very confusing, difficult to maintain and test, and therefore bug-proneness. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- **[Extract function]:** When a function uses a conditional statement with many different branches, each responsible for handling a specific error type, we can use this refactoring to delegate each branch (i.e., handling of a response type) to a different new private function. This approach makes the code cleaner, more concise, and readable.
- **[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter]:** Another possibility is to use this refactoring to break down complex branching into a multi-clause function, where each clause handles a different error type. This approach enhances readability and maintainability by organizing the code according to distinct error scenarios.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[GenServer envy]** smell? *

This smell occurs when a *Task* or *Agent* is used but handled as if it were a *GenServer*. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. **[Generalise a process abstraction]**: When an *Agent* or *Task* goes beyond its suggested use cases and becomes painful, it is better to refactor it into a *GenServer* using this operation.
2. **[Introduce processes]**: When we finish generalizing a process, it may still be insufficient to achieve an optimal mapping with the parallel activities of the problem being solved. In these circumstances, we can use this refactoring to remove bottlenecks.
3. **[Register a process]**: When we create a new process, we can also use this refactoring to assign a user-defined name to the new process ID and use that user-defined name instead of the process ID in message passing.
4. **[Remove dead code]**: When we are generalizing a process *Agent* or *Task* into a *GenServer*, naturally, some functions of the module that represented the original process may become useless and can therefore be removed.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[Divergent change]** smell? *

This smell occurs when a single module is frequently modified in multiple places for unrelated reasons. Modules that group together many functions that do not share a common purpose are prone to Divergent Change. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. **[Splitting a large module]**: This smell can be removed by creating new cohesive modules and moving related functions into them.
 2. **[Rename an identifier]**: In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.
- **[Moving a definition]**: If there is already a module *B* that is more suitable to accommodate a function that makes module *A* less cohesive, we can simply move this function from module *A* to module *B* to remove this smell.
 - **[Behaviour extraction]**: This smell can be removed by creating a new cohesive module *B* and moving related functions of module *A* into it. Thereby, we can use this refactoring to transform module *A* into a *behaviour definition* and create module *B* as a *behaviour implementation* of module *A*, thus achieving this goal.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[Modules with identical names]** smell? *

This code smell is related to possible module name conflicts that can occur when a library is implemented. Due to a limitation of the Erlang VM (BEAM), also used by Elixir, only one instance of a module can be loaded at a time. If there are name conflicts between more than one module, they will be considered the same by BEAM and only one of them will be loaded. This can cause unwanted code behavior. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- **[Rename an identifier]:** In Elixir, there is a naming convention for modules that should be followed when implementing libraries. According to this convention, a library should use its own name as a prefix (namespace) for all its module names (e.g., `LibraryName.ModuleName`). When a library does not adhere to this naming convention, it can lead to name conflicts for the library's clients. To remove this smell, we can rename the modules of a library to adapt them to this convention. It is important to be careful when performing this refactoring on already released libraries, as it may cause breaking changes in client code.
 - **[Move file]:** If the same directory contains two modules with the same name defined in different files, we can use this refactoring to relocate one of these modules to a new directory. Naturally, we will also need to rename the moved module to conform to the naming convention for modules in Elixir, which recommends using the directory name as a prefix (namespace) for all module names contained within it (e.g., `LibraryName.ModuleName`).
1. **[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition]:** As explained in the previous refactoring, when a library does not follow the naming convention for modules, it can lead to name conflicts in their clients. To remove this smell in already released libraries, we can use this present refactoring on the modules of a library, adapting the names of the copies to this convention. Meanwhile, the modules with names outside the convention should be marked as deprecated but not immediately removed, to avoid breaking client code.
 2. **[Remove dead code]:** When modules deprecated by the previous refactoring have remained deprecated long enough for clients to adapt to the new naming conventions, we can use this refactoring to permanently eliminate them, thereby removing the risk of name conflicts.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[Agent obsession]** smell? *

This smell occurs when the responsibility for interacting with an Agent process is spread across the system. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. **[Generalise a function definition]:** When functions responsible for directly interacting with the *Agent* are scattered throughout the system, it indicates the presence of this smell. We can refactor them simultaneously using this operation, centralizing the responsibility for interacting with the *Agent* in a single module or function.
 2. **[Moving a definition]:** After generalizing the functions that were originally responsible for directly accessing the *Agent*, the generic function created to centralize this task might not be located in the most appropriate module. This refactoring can be used to address this issue.
 3. **[Add or remove a parameter]:** Functions that were originally responsible for directly accessing the *Agent*, once generalized by the previous refactoring, may require the addition of new parameters to be passed to the generic function called within their bodies.
- **[Behaviour extraction]:** One way to remove this smell is to define a *behaviour* containing a contract that specifies the format of all functions intended to interact with an *Agent* throughout the system. Following this refactoring, all modules that wish to access the *Agent* must implement this extracted *behaviour*.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Working with invalid data\]](#) smell? *

This code smell refers to a function that does not validate its parameters' types and therefore can produce internal non-predicted behavior. When an error is raised inside a function due to an invalid parameter value, this can confuse the developers and make it harder to locate and fix the error. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): When a library function does not validate the types of its parameters at its signature, we can at least use this refactoring to document these data. This will help the clients of this function (i.e., third-party code) to protect themselves from potential errors caused by invalid data.
 2. [\[Add type declarations and contracts\]](#): If recurring data structures are found when documenting functions of a library, these structures can be named using the present refactoring, thus creating new reusable data types and increasing the system's readability.
- [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): Optionally, if a client validates the data passed to a library function call using traditional conditional statements, we can use this refactoring to make the client function more idiomatic while still addressing the smell.
 - [\[Struct guard to matching\]](#): Optionally, if a guard clause involving the functions `is_struct/1` or `is_struct/2` is used to avoid working with invalid data, we can use this refactoring to simplify the code used to remove this code smell.
 - [\[Simplifying guard sequences\]](#): Optionally, if a guard clause with redundancies is used to avoid working with invalid data, we can use the present refactoring to also simplify the code used to remove this code smell.
 - [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): Optionally, we can replace guard clauses used in a multi-clause client function to handle invalid data with traditional conditional statements. By doing so, we can use this refactoring to consolidate all data type validations into a single-clause function.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Complex extractions in clauses\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function uses pattern matching in its signature to extract values that are used both in guard checks and in the function body. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Simplifying pattern matching with nested structs\]](#): When using pattern matching to perform deep extraction in nested `structs` passed as parameters to a clause of a multi-clause function, we may create unnecessarily messy and hard-to-understand code. With this refactoring, we can simplify this kind of extraction by performing pattern matching only on the outermost `struct` in the nesting, instead of matching patterns with very internal `structs`.
 - [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): To prevent complex extractions in clauses, which are used both to access data extracted in guard clauses and in the function body, from making the code confusing, we can use this refactoring to replace all guards with traditional conditionals, consolidating them into a single clause for the function. This way, all extracted data will be used exclusively in the function body.
 - [\[Equality guard to pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, if an unnecessary temporary variable is extracted from a `struct's` field in a clause of a multi-clause function and is only used for an equality comparison in a guard, this refactoring can simplify the pattern matching in that clause.
 - [\[Struct guard to matching\]](#): Optionally, if some clauses of a multi-clause function use guard clauses involving the functions `is_struct/1` or `is_struct/2`, this refactoring can simplify the pattern matching performed by these clauses.
 - [\[Remove unnecessary calls to length/1\]](#): If a list extraction is performed in a function clause only to use it in an unnecessary call to `length/1` in a guard clause, this extraction can be replaced by using pattern matching directly, eliminating the need for the guard clause. To do this, use this refactoring.
 - [\[Function clauses to/from case clauses\]](#): When complex extractions are done in clauses of multi-clause functions, making it difficult to understand which data is used inside or outside the function body, we can use this refactoring to transform a multi-clause function into a single clause function. By doing this, we will map the function's clauses into clauses of a case statement, ensuring that all extractions occur within the function body.
1. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): When we are moving an extraction performed in a function clause into its body, we can initially use this refactoring to duplicate within the function body an extraction performed in the signature.
 2. [\[Temporary variable elimination\]](#): After duplicating the complex extraction within the function body, we can use this operation to remove unnecessary extracted parts, thereby cleaning up the code.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

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Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

[Voltar](#)

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